

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' NATIONAL FEELING, PRIDE BASED ON A COMPETENT APPROACH

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Abstract: In this article, based on the competent approach, the development of national and general cultural competences in students is studied, its necessity and pedagogical relevance today are covered in detail.

Key words: pedagogue, professional competence, classification, improvement, competence, competent approach, feelings of national feeling, pride.

INTRODUCTION. Today, the general cultural approach has begun to be considered from the point of view of various humanitarian sciences: sociology, pedagogy, psychology. The main principle of the universal approach is that the replacement of the fundamental principles of national, social and cultural changes with another one is the most important event in the history of mankind, even more than the change of the form of government, because the important changes in society are "fundamental and epochal revolution in human culture" from the beginning. forgives

Social and cultural activity is a powerful means of influencing the spiritual and moral formation of a person, his worldview, as well as an integral multifaceted field of activity that contributes to the formation of motives, values, views, etc. It creates conditions for a person to realize himself, reveal his abilities, satisfy and develop his cultural needs. National and cross-cultural competence is the most important basis for a stable position and human success in a multicultural world.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Issues of development of socio-cultural activity among future teachers in Uzbekistan M. Rakhmanova, M. Kuronov, H. Tojiboyeva, G.J. Tulenova, Q. Quranboyev; N. Abdumuratova, D. Nafasov regarding the development of socio-cultural competence; historical-philosophical, ethical-aesthetic content of spiritual and artistic values , O. Abdurakhmonov, D. Yakibova, R. Mavlonova, N. Rakhmonkulova have conducted studies on the development of thinking capabilities of learners based on the person-oriented approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. National feeling, feelings of pride and pride are formed on the basis of feelings such as love for the Motherland, joy in understanding the national culture, understanding the truth of political actions and ideas that serve the national development and the benefit of the people.

What is national feeling? According to the literature, the national feeling reflects the important relationship of the subject to the object. The feelings of a person have a psychophysiological nature, the national feeling, which is a rare phenomenon of social psychology, is formed under the influence of individual feelings specific to the subject. Kindness based on the feeling of national pride, pride in being a child of the nation, love for people, mutual care, compassion, putting the interests of others before one's own interests, tolerance, feelings of not being indifferent to the destiny of the homeland, sorrow over tragedies in the history of the nation, nobility, self-sacrifice, patriotism, internationalism, hard work, admiration, pride in the glorious history and national heroes are evident.

The Russian philosopher I. Ilin in his writings emphasizes the importance of having a sense of patriotism for the representatives of the nation in ensuring national development, and emphasizes the need to develop this feeling in the individual. According to the scientist, patriotism is manifested in the form of: official patriotism, compulsory patriotism (compulsory military service) and real patriotism. The first two aspects will never instill in a person a feeling of love for the Motherland, on the contrary, it can create a negative attitude towards the Motherland due to the blind imposition of various obligations on the person. Therefore, it is necessary to awaken the feeling of love for the Motherland in young people without any coercion [3]. The author emphasizes that the role of educators is of special importance in this place, not that he propagates the need to love the Motherland among the youth, but that he himself believes in the Motherland and sets an example with his personal actions. says that it has a strong effect.

The essence of the concept of national feeling is revealed in the works of O. Bauer. "Close acquaintance with other nationalities often awakens a feeling of love and pride for one's own nation," the author emphasizes, "but the power of this love is different in different classes and individuals of society. appears" [1]. The views of the author in this regard confirm that it is appropriate to use effective tools that help to educate them to the sense of internationalism within the framework of organizing national education among students.

The study of sources related to the problem made it possible to conclude that the process of developing national competence is based on the following logical sequence:

1. Education of national belonging is a state, a status that expresses that a person is a representative of a certain nation. This concept also serves to express the

surname of a person. After all, the nationality of the parents or the dynasty guarantees that the children will have the characteristics of this nationality.

2. The formation of national feeling and mentality is an important attitude of the subject to the object, a feature reflected in the content of this attitude, which is manifested in social relations and the influence of the individual on the environment. A person with a national feeling should be able to feel that he is a representative of the nation, and his lifestyle should be compatible with that of his compatriots.

3. Manifestation of the national character is a set of stable mental characteristics reflected in the mentality of the representatives of the nation, which is also reflected in the relationship to social existence. The integrity of the lifestyle, social goals, life activities and spiritual experiences of the representatives of the nation serve to express the leading mental characteristics of the national character.

4. Development of national consciousness - the level of conscious approach to the effective organization of social relations and life activities based on national values by people belonging to a certain nationality. Philosophical sources define the concept of "national consciousness" as follows: "the single language, customs, traditions, values and spirituality of the nation are an important criterion for the development from the bottom up, from the simple to the complex. In turn, the development of national consciousness raises the level of self-awareness of each nation" [5].

5. National self-awareness - every nation (nation) sees itself as a real entity, a representative of certain material and spiritual wealth, a single language, customs, traditions, values and belonging to the state, interests and to understand the generality of needs [5]. National self-awareness serves a proper assessment of the role of the nation in the world community and its impact on the overall development.

6. Cultivation of national pride is an internal mental mood that occurs as a result of self-awareness of each nation. This feeling is a feeling of pride in one's motherland, in the material and spiritual heritage left by the ancestors, in the contribution of one's nation to the world civilization, in the dignity and respect of other nations. After all, "national freedom is formed in every person as a result of mastering the material and spiritual heritage of his nation, perfectly knowing its customs, traditions, values, history and comparing it with other nations, and in it his own increases his love for his nation" [5]. Possessing national pride as a representative of the nation does not only express pride in

the achievements achieved by the nation to which it belongs during the historical development, in the nation's contribution to the world civilization, but also to fight for national development, the fate and prospects of the nation, in this regard and a deep sense of responsibility.

7. Formation of national pride is a high stage of possessing a sense of national pride, which is the nation's "conscious feeling that it is a complete social unit" [2]. Possessing a sense of national pride also represents the place in the history of the nation's personal development, its worthy contribution to world civilization, its dignity, reputation, and trust in the nation's prospects.

Analyzing different views, we can conclude that this concept of "general cultural competence" is very multifaceted. So, I. E. Riske and others define it as one aspect of communicative ability, D. S. Melnikova socio-cultural competence as the ability to communicate sufficiently, G. V. Yelizarova, E. N. Solovova and others consider it a set of socio-cultural knowledge; P.V. Sisoyev considers socio-cultural competence as a set of values, behavior models, customs and traditions. G.A. Vorobyev considers national and universal cultural competence as a complex phenomenon and distinguishes the following interrelated components in its structure:

- linguistic and local studies component (lexical units of national and cultural essence and the ability to use them in the context of intercultural communication);
- sociolinguistic component (linguistic characteristics of representatives of social strata, different generations, genders, social groups, dialects);
- socio-psychological component (social- and cultural-conditional scenarios, national specific behavior models and the use of communication technologies accepted in this culture);
- cultural component (socio-cultural, historical-cultural, ethno-cultural background).

L.A. Lukyanova defines the following knowledge, skills, qualifications and abilities as the leading structural features of a person's general cultural competence, which is formed within the framework of general cultural competence:

- knowledge of the value system of national and foreign cultures;
- knowledge of national symbols;
- knowledge of culturally oriented words and phraseology;

- to know the social and cultural characteristics of speech behavior of representatives of national and foreign cultures, their compatibility and incompatibility;
 - lead to socio-cultural barriers in communication
- to know the possible socio-cultural characteristics that are not taken into account;
- to have an understanding of cultural-historical values, traditions and norms of interaction between representatives of different social groups in the studied society;
 - skills to recognize linguistic units and realities with socio-cultural characteristics operating in the studied areas of intercultural communication and to use them correctly in speech; skills of translating socio-culturally determined linguistic units from a foreign language into a local language and from a local language into a foreign language;
 - the ability to adequately interpret and respond to events and relationships in real conditions in accordance with the norms of foreign language culture in speech and outside speech;
 - the ability to communicate interculturally;
 - freedom from prejudices against representatives of other cultures;
 - tolerance to the manifestation of something foreign to us in other cultures; the ability to perceive a stranger with positive emotions;
 - willingness to communicate: the desire and ability to actively communicate with representatives of other socio-cultural communities;
 - socio-cultural observation;
 - socio-cultural tolerance [4].

CONCLUSION. Thus, the analysis of various scientific approaches suggests that national and universal competence is considered as a part of communicative ability (I.E. Riske and others), as the ability to conduct appropriate communication (D.S. Melnikova), as a complex of social and cultural knowledge, behavioral models, made it possible to determine that it is considered as a collection of customs and traditions (P.V. Sisoyev). In conclusion, national and universal competence is based on vital knowledge and skills that are formed based on the social requirements of today. Such knowledge and skills are based on national and cultural values.

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